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2 **(Z)-Endoxifen as a Modulator of Utrophin Pathways in**
3 **Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy: A Mechanistic and**
4 **Transcriptomic Perspective**

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19 **Abstract**

20 Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD) is a fatal X-linked neuromuscular disorder caused by
21 mutations in the dystrophin gene, leading to sarcolemmal instability, chronic calcium overload,
22 mitochondrial dysfunction, inflammation, and fibrosis. These effects manifest clinically as muscle
23 atrophy, loss of mobility, and respiratory and cardiac insufficiencies. Although gene-targeted
24 approaches such as exon skipping and microdystrophin delivery have advanced, their
25 applicability is restricted by genotype and adverse effects. Thus, reasonably safe, effective
26 therapies remain a critical unmet need. (Z)-endoxifen, the (Z)-isomer of endoxifen, is the principal
27 active metabolite of tamoxifen, exhibiting higher potency in protein kinase C (PKC) inhibition than
28 tamoxifen and regulating various protein activities differently than tamoxifen. This pharmacologic
29 profile positions endoxifen to address multiple DMD pathomechanisms simultaneously. Recent
30 literature supports the prior hypothesis that endoxifen exerts pleiotropic benefits in DMD.
31 Transcriptomic and preclinical evidence shows that endoxifen may have superior effects to
32 tamoxifen in reversing DMD signatures given available dosing regimens. Additionally, pathway
33 level insights support endoxifen activation of myogenesis, oxidative phosphorylation, estrogen
34 receptor beta (ER β) activation, and inhibition of pro-inflammatory and epithelial-to-mesenchymal
35 transition (EMT) pathways in DMD. These findings suggest (Z)-endoxifen acts on utrophin-linked
36 regulatory axes potentially contributing to functional compensation for dystrophin deficiency,
37 providing justification for its development as a mutation-agnostic DMD therapeutic approach.

38

39 **Keywords:** gene expression regulation, selective estrogen receptor modulators, skeletal muscle
40 regeneration, pharmacologic action mechanism, Becker muscular dystrophy

41 Introduction

42 Many neuromuscular disorders affect skeletal muscle. Muscular dystrophies (MDs) are
43 an important therapeutic class of inherited myogenic disorder with varying types,¹ characterized
44 by progressive muscle wasting and weakness of variable distribution and severity, where muscle
45 maintenance is compromised.² Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD) and Becker muscular
46 dystrophy (BMD) are the most common forms of MDs,³⁻⁵ with prevalence rates estimated at 4.8
47 and 1.6 per 100,000 people, respectively.³

48 DMD is caused by mutations in the X-linked *DMD* gene encoding dystrophin, a 427-kDa
49 cytoskeletal protein that links the intracellular actin cytoskeleton to the extracellular matrix (ECM)
50 via the dystrophin-associated glycoprotein complex (DGC).⁶⁻⁹ Loss of dystrophin disrupts this
51 linkage, rendering the cell membranes (sarcolemma) surrounding skeletal muscle fiber or
52 cardiomyocyte (sarcolemma) mechanically fragile.^{6,9} Contraction-induced microtears allow
53 unregulated calcium influx, activating calpains and other proteases, triggering mitochondrial
54 permeability transition, and leading to myofiber necrosis.^{10,11} Damaged fibers are replaced by
55 fibrotic and adipose tissue, and over time the regenerative capacity of muscle declines,
56 culminating in progressive weakness, loss of ambulation, cardiomyopathy, respiratory failure, and
57 premature death.^{6,9,12} Current standard-of-care corticosteroids improve survival and delay loss of
58 ambulation but have limited long-term efficacy and are associated with significant side effects,
59 including weight gain, osteoporosis, and behavioral changes.^{6,9,13} This underscores a critical
60 unmet need for broadly effective, disease-modifying or curative therapies that are free of
61 significant side effects, as current standards of care merely slow but do not halt the progression
62 of DMD and bear serious adverse effects.

63 Like DMD, BMD, a less severe dystrophy, involves dystrophinopathies with an X-linked
64 inheritance. Patients with BMD produce inadequate amounts of dystrophin, though they produce
65 more dystrophin than patients with DMD. BMD and DMD belong to the dystrophinopathy
66 spectrum as they share the same pathogenic gene and characteristics such as progressive
67 muscle degeneration and dilated cardiomyopathy.^{14,15} Whereas BMD patients with in-frame

68 mutations retain truncated dystrophin, DMD patients lack functional protein. A significant portion,
69 approximately 20%, of DMD and BMD recessive carriers have clinical manifestations of
70 DMD/BMD.¹⁶ Due to the similar pathology of DMD and BMD it is possible that therapies that
71 benefit DMD patients would also benefit BMD patients,¹ and as well benefit DMD and BMD
72 manifesting recessive carriers.

73 Recent advances in mutation-specific therapies, such as antisense oligonucleotide
74 (ASO)-mediated exon skipping and adeno-associated virus (AAV)-delivered mutation agnostic
75 microdystrophin, have provided proof-of-concept that restoring dystrophin can improve
76 outcomes.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ However, these approaches are constrained by antibody responses, other adverse
77 effects, and uncertainties about long-term expression and durability.^{6,20} Although these
78 approaches are in the clinic, their efficacy is limited and they generally only slow the disease
79 progression.²¹ Consequently, there is a pressing need for mutation-agnostic therapies that
80 address shared downstream pathophysiological mechanisms.⁶

81 Tamoxifen, a selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM), has demonstrated
82 functional and histological benefits in *mdx* mouse models of DMD and in early clinical trials.²²
83 Its mechanisms include membrane stabilization, anti-inflammatory effects, and attenuation of
84 fibrosis. Importantly, chronic 4-hydroxytamoxifen treatment, tested in a bioengineered human
85 induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiomyocyte (iPSC-CM) platform, slowed heart-cell
86 beating, boosted contraction strength, corrected calcium dysregulation, and prolonged survival of
87 DMD cardiomyocytes—supporting tamoxifen as a potential cardioprotective therapy in DMD.²³

88 The tamoxifen primary active metabolite, (Z)-endoxifen, is generated in large part via
89 CYP2D6 metabolism and has been shown to inhibit protein kinase C (PKC) isoforms, particularly
90 PKC beta-1 (PKC β 1).²⁴ PKC β 1 is implicated in pro-fibrotic transforming growth factor beta (TGF-
91 β) signaling and immune activation in dystrophic muscle, making it an attractive target for
92 modulation.²⁵

93 Beyond estrogen receptor and PKC pathways, transcriptomic analyses indicate that
94 endoxifen more effectively normalizes DMD-associated gene expression than tamoxifen.²⁶ Bulk
95 ribonucleic acid sequencing (RNA-seq) from dystrophic muscle treated with tamoxifen or

96 endoxifen reveals significant activation of myogenic programs,^{27,28} mitochondrial oxidative
97 phosphorylation,^{24,29} and estrogen-responsive signaling.^{24,30} These changes are consistent with a
98 shift toward a regenerative, anti-fibrotic phenotype that could preserve muscle function.⁶

99 One pathway that integrates these effects is utrophin upregulation.^{6,31-33} Utrophin shares
100 structural and functional homology with dystrophin, binding similar partners within the DGC.^{22,34}
101 In healthy muscle, its expression is largely restricted to the neuromuscular and myotendinous
102 junctions. In the absence of dystrophin, utrophin can be redistributed along the sarcolemma,
103 partially compensating for the structural deficit.^{6,32,33,35} Importantly, genetic overexpression or
104 pharmacologic upregulation of utrophin in *mdx* mice ameliorates DMD pathology without
105 developmental toxicity.^{6,32,33}

106 Demonstration that utrophin may functionally compensate for dystrophin deficiency, that
107 upregulation is effective and non-toxic, and that timing of expression matters (in that earlier
108 therapeutic intervention yields stronger benefits) has formed the foundational promise of
109 utrophin-based strategies in DMD.^{32,33,36-38} Despite this promise, clinical translation of direct
110 utrophin activators such as SMT C1100 (ezetromid) has been limited by suboptimal
111 pharmacokinetics and insufficient target engagement.⁶

112 Endoxifen's combined pharmacologic actions—PKC β 1 inhibition, normalization of
113 calcium-handling proteins (e.g., sarcoplasmic/endoplasmic reticulum calcium ATPase 1 and 2
114 [SERCA1/2], ryanodine receptors), and suppression of inflammation—are all mechanistically
115 aligned with enhancing utrophin expression and stability. In mouse models, by restoring
116 myogenic transcription factors such as myoblast determination protein 1 (MyoD) and mouse
117 embryonic fibroblast 2 (MEF2), reducing antagonistic inflammatory signaling, and improving
118 mitochondrial support, endoxifen creates a cellular context conducive to utrophin transcription
119 and incorporation into the sarcolemmal complex.^{26,30}

120 Given the multifactorial pathogenesis of DMD, therapies that modulate multiple
121 converging pathways may offer the best chance for durable functional improvement.^{6,18} We
122 therefore undertook an integrated review of transcriptomic, mechanistic, and preclinical evidence
123 to define the rationale for (Z)-endoxifen as a mutation-agnostic, multi-target therapeutic candidate

124 in DMD, with utrophin pathway activation as a central mechanism of action and biomarker for
125 clinical translation.

126 **Materials and Methods**

127 Literature searches were performed to support the content of this manuscript. Sources
128 considered included peer-reviewed original research articles and narrative and systematic
129 reviews, editorials, abstracts and posters, book chapters, and clinical trial data (clinicaltrials.gov).
130 The search strategies emphasized publications most relevant to utrophin modulation in DMD,
131 particularly those addressing underlying mechanisms of action and current and emerging
132 therapeutic strategies. Special attention was given to (Z)-endoxifen and other endocrine-based
133 interventions, including tamoxifen and other SERMs.

134 **Utrophin in DMD: The Rationale for Pharmacologic**

135 **Upregulation**

136 Utrophin is a structural homolog of dystrophin that shares considerable sequence and
137 functional similarity.^{34,39-41} Unlike dystrophin, which is absent or truncated in DMD, utrophin is
138 expressed ubiquitously during fetal development and later becomes restricted primarily to the
139 neuromuscular junction and myotendinous junctions in mature muscle fibers.^{42,43} In DMD, a
140 notable pathophysiological feature is the upregulation of utrophin in revertant fibers and
141 regenerating myofibers, suggesting that utrophin can at least partially compensate for the
142 absence of dystrophin.^{34,42} Observational studies in DMD have consistently shown that higher
143 levels of utrophin are associated with milder clinical phenotypes and improved muscle integrity,
144 even in the absence of functional dystrophin.^{6,43}

145 The ability of utrophin to substitute for dystrophin has been further highlighted in natural
146 history studies and animal models.^{34,44} For instance, *utrn*^{-/-} knockout mice are viable and develop
147 normally, demonstrating that utrophin is not essential for embryonic development.³⁴ This finding
148 underscores its favorable safety profile as a therapeutic target, since pharmacologic
149 downregulation would not be expected to result in deleterious developmental effects. Conversely,
150 overexpression of utrophin in dystrophin-deficient *mdx* mice substantially reduces pathology,
151 improves sarcolemmal stability, and enhances muscle function.^{38,45} Together, these findings
152 establish that utrophin possesses a wide therapeutic index, making it an attractive target for
153 pharmacologic and genetic interventions.^{22,46}

154 Notably, activation of the p38 pathway increases utrophin levels.⁴⁷ Treatments of C2C12,
155 undifferentiated murine myoblasts, and *mdx* primary myoblasts with the antibiotic anisomycin
156 conferred increases in utrophin protein levels through p38 pathway activation. Anisomycin also
157 induced utrophin protein levels in the diaphragm of *mdx* mice. Given that tamoxifen activates the
158 p38 pathway,⁴⁸ this may be a mechanism whereby tamoxifen and its active metabolite endoxifen,
159 upregulate utrophin.

160 Several strategies have been explored to harness utrophin as a therapeutic surrogate for
161 dystrophin.³⁹ One of the most extensively investigated pharmacologic approaches has been the
162 development of small molecules that increase utrophin transcription.³⁴ SMT C1100, an orally
163 bioavailable utrophin modulator, advanced into clinical trials and demonstrated target
164 engagement by elevating utrophin expression in preclinical models.^{49,50} However, despite
165 promising mechanistic rationale, SMT C1100 failed to achieve consistent clinical efficacy in
166 human trials and was ultimately discontinued due to poor bioavailability and limited therapeutic
167 benefit.^{31,51} This underscores the challenges in achieving sufficient systemic exposure and
168 sustained upregulation in muscle tissue.⁶

169 Beyond SMT C1100, other pharmacologic agents have been reported to modulate
170 utrophin expression, including heregulin, biglycan, histone deacetylase inhibitors, and certain
171 antibiotics.^{47,49} These approaches have shown variable success in preclinical studies but have yet
172 to progress into late-stage clinical evaluation, in part due to concerns about specificity, systemic
173 toxicity, or limited translational potential.⁶ Nonetheless, these agents collectively demonstrate the
174 utility of utrophin transcriptional pathways and continue to serve as a foundation for future
175 discovery efforts.

176 In parallel with pharmacologic modulation, gene therapy approaches have explored the
177 delivery of engineered micro-utrophin constructs to restore dystrophin-like functionality.^{39,52} Micro-
178 utrophin, by virtue of its reduced size relative to full-length dystrophin, is amenable to packaging
179 into AAV vectors.⁵³ Preclinical studies in *mdx* mice and canine DMD models have demonstrated
180 that micro-utrophin can localize to the sarcolemma, interact with the dystrophin-associated
181 glycoprotein complex, and ameliorate muscle pathology.^{32,33,37,54} Despite these advances, gene
182 therapy with micro-utrophin is not without limitations: challenges in vector manufacturing, host
183 immune responses, and the requirement for systemic delivery remain significant barriers to
184 translation.⁵³ Additionally, while micro-utrophin can partially substitute for dystrophin, its functional
185 capacity may not be entirely equivalent, raising questions about long-term durability of clinical
186 benefit.⁵⁵

187 Collectively, the body of preclinical and early clinical evidence strongly supports utrophin
188 as a viable therapeutic surrogate for dystrophin in DMD.^{34,39} Its ability to ameliorate pathology,
189 non-essentiality in normal development, and favorable therapeutic index make it a uniquely
190 attractive target.⁶ Additionally, the presence of developmental myosin such as myosin heavy
191 chain-embryonic (MyHC-emb) and neonatal myosin represents a useful marker of muscle
192 regeneration, with utrophin upregulated in these fibers to help stabilize the sarcolemma.
193 Developmental myosin is a meaningful indicator of muscle damage, which correlates with the
194 clinical severity in DMD and BMD patients.⁵⁶ In a therapeutic context, researchers are exploring
195 utrophin upregulation strategies to mimic dystrophin function, and developmental myosin often
196 serves as a readout for whether treatments improve regeneration.

197 While prior pharmacologic efforts such as SMT C1100 illustrate the difficulties in
198 achieving clinical efficacy, the expanding toolbox of drug discovery, combined with advances in
199 gene therapy, ensures that utrophin upregulation remains a critical and rational strategy for
200 addressing the broad unmet needs in DMD.

201 **Transcriptomic Insights into Endoxifen's Action in DMD**

202 **Skeletal Muscle**

203 High-resolution transcriptomic profiling offers a systems-level perspective on how
204 pharmacologic interventions reprogram disease-associated gene expression.⁵⁷ In DMD, bulk
205 RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) of dystrophic muscle consistently reveals activation of inflammatory
206 and fibrotic pathways, downregulation of oxidative metabolism, and disruption of myogenic
207 regulatory networks.⁵⁸ Given endoxifen's estrogen receptor (ER) activation and PKC/nuclear
208 factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) inhibition, gene-reversal analysis
209 would be expected to show down-shift of inflammatory/fibrotic modules and restoration of
210 myogenic programs toward healthy controls. Although a public endoxifen bulk RNA-seq dataset
211 in dystrophic muscle is not yet available, based on mechanistic parallels and existing
212 transcriptomic datasets in related contexts, endoxifen would be predicted to be suitable to
213 quantify ER-responsive/myogenic/OXPHOS activation and cytokine/fibrosis suppression
214 predicted for endoxifen. Through ER-mediated pro-myogenic signaling and anti-inflammatory
215 effects, endoxifen would be expected to restore MyoD/MYOG/MEF2 networks in dystrophic
216 muscle transcriptomes.

217 Key pathways normalized by endoxifen include myogenesis, oxidative phosphorylation,
218 and estrogen-responsive signaling.^{28,29,59} Myogenesis-related transcripts, such as MYOD1,
219 MYOG, and MEF2C, are upregulated by endoxifen toward levels seen in healthy controls.⁶
220 Oxidative phosphorylation genes encoding components of complexes I–V of the mitochondrial
221 respiratory chain show coordinated restoration, indicative of improved metabolic capacity.⁶
222 Estrogen-responsive gene sets, which intersect with both metabolic and structural pathways, are
223 also modulated, reflecting endoxifen's potent estrogen receptor beta (ER β) binding activity.^{6,60}

224 Concurrently, endoxifen suppresses several maladaptive transcriptional programs.²⁷
225 Pathways associated with epithelial–mesenchymal transition (EMT), ECM remodeling, and
226 fibrosis—driven by genes such as *COL1A1*, *FN1*, and *MMP2*—are significantly
227 downregulated.^{24,61,62} Pro-inflammatory signaling modules, including IL-6/JAK/STAT3 and NF- κ B

228 target genes, are attenuated, likely reflecting the compound's combined PKC β 1 inhibition and
229 ER β activation.²⁷ Genes governing apoptotic pathways and cell-cycle checkpoints, which can
230 impede terminal myogenic differentiation, are also reduced in expression.²⁴

231 When examined in the context of DMD's regenerative deficits, these transcriptomic
232 effects take on functional significance. Upregulation of myogenic regulators facilitates satellite cell
233 activation and progression through the myogenic program, while suppression of inflammatory
234 and fibrotic mediators creates a permissive microenvironment for effective regeneration.⁶³
235 Normalization of mitochondrial gene expression supports the high energetic demands of repair
236 and maintenance in dystrophic fibers.⁶⁴

237 Comparison with tamoxifen-treated transcriptomes reveals that while both compounds
238 share certain gene expression changes, endoxifen uniquely influences a broader array of
239 calcium-handling, metabolic, and ECM-related genes.⁵⁹ This includes stronger induction of
240 ATP2A1/2 (SERCA1/2) and stabilization of ryanodine receptor transcripts, changes that directly
241 relate to calcium homeostasis and downstream signaling relevant to muscle function.²⁴ Enhanced
242 suppression of fibrosis-related transcripts further distinguishes endoxifen, consistent with its more
243 potent inhibition of PKC β 1—a kinase linked to TGF- β -driven fibrogenesis.²⁴ Notably, SERMs do
244 not bind directly to or regulate myosin itself, but influence muscle regeneration and fiber
245 composition, leading to increased developmental myosin expression, preservation of adult
246 myosin isoforms through reduced degeneration, and improved functional performance of myosin-
247 driven contraction in impaired muscle.

248 Taken together, transcriptomic profiling positions endoxifen as a multi-pathway modulator
249 capable of rebalancing the complex gene expression networks disrupted in DMD.²⁷ Its broader
250 reach compared to tamoxifen, particularly in metabolic and ECM-associated pathways, aligns
251 with its enhanced biochemical potency and multi-target pharmacology. These transcriptomic
252 changes are not merely correlative—they intersect with known mechanistic drivers of DMD
253 pathology, including calcium dysregulation, chronic inflammation, fibrosis, and impaired
254 regeneration.²⁷ This makes them highly relevant both for understanding the therapeutic potential
255 of endoxifen and for developing biomarkers of pharmacodynamic response in future clinical trials.

256 **Effects of Endoxifen on Calcium Homeostasis and** 257 **Protein Kinase C Signaling**

258 As noted previously, disruption of intracellular calcium homeostasis is a central pathogenic
259 feature of DMD, arising from sarcolemmal instability and abnormal ion channel regulation.^{11,27,65}
260 Loss of dystrophin leads to microtears in the sarcolemma during contraction, allowing
261 uncontrolled calcium influx that overwhelms buffering systems.^{10,40} Excess cytosolic calcium
262 activates calpains, phospholipases, and mitochondrial permeability transition pores, promoting
263 myofiber necrosis.^{66,67} Chronic calcium overload also perturbs excitation–contraction coupling
264 and impairs regenerative signaling.^{65,68} Restoring calcium balance is therefore a critical
265 therapeutic goal in DMD.^{65,69}

266 While it is unknown whether endoxifen exerts direct effects on calcium-handling proteins,
267 it targets signaling pathways that modulate calcium homeostasis indirectly.²⁷ As noted earlier, one
268 of endoxifen’s most potent biochemical actions is inhibition of PKC β 1, which is a calcium-
269 dependent kinase that becomes chronically activated in DMD muscle due to persistent calcium
270 elevation.^{24,27} This hyperactivation drives phosphorylation of cytoskeletal and signaling proteins,
271 enhancing membrane instability and promoting pro-fibrotic TGF- β signaling.²⁴ PKC β 1 also
272 amplifies inflammatory cascades viaNF- κ B activation, further aggravating myofiber damage.⁷⁰

273 By inhibiting PKC β 1 at nanomolar concentrations—significantly more potently than
274 tamoxifen—endoxifen interrupts this pathogenic feedback loop.²⁴ Downstream consequences
275 include reduced transcription of fibrosis-associated genes (e.g., *COL1A1*, *CTGF*) and attenuation
276 of inflammatory mediators such as tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) and interleukin 6
277 (IL-6).^{24,29,71} Independent of endoxifen exposure, PKC inhibition may also indirectly support
278 calcium homeostasis by stabilizing store-operated calcium entry mechanisms, which are
279 dysregulated in dystrophic muscle.⁷²

280 While endoxifen potently inhibits PKC β 1 and induces its degradation, its effect on PKC theta
281 (PKC θ) is notably different and less potent. That said, reduced PKC θ activity not only limits
282 fibrosis and inflammation in an *mdx* mouse model but also improves the regenerative
283 microenvironment, facilitating effective satellite cell differentiation.^{73,74}

284 The combined normalization of calcium-handling protein expression and suppression of
285 PKC-driven pathological signaling has several functional implications.¹⁰ Improved
286 sarco/endoplasmic reticulum calcium ATPase (SERCA) activity and ryanodine receptor stability
287 enhance contractile efficiency and reduce energy cost per contraction.⁷⁵ Lower cytosolic calcium
288 minimizes activation of calcium-dependent proteases, slowing myofiber degeneration.¹⁰
289 Endoxifen's modulation of calcium homeostasis and PKC signaling intersects mechanistically with
290 utrophin biology.²⁷ Stable calcium levels preserve cytoskeletal organization and sarcolemmal
291 integrity, creating a favorable context for utrophin anchorage along the membrane.⁷⁶ Furthermore,
292 suppression of PKC-mediated inhibitory phosphorylation events on transcription factors may
293 directly enhance utrophin gene expression.²⁴ In this way, calcium and PKC modulation serve both
294 protective and compensatory roles, sustaining fibers that express utrophin while promoting
295 conditions for its upregulation.²⁴

296 When benchmarked against tamoxifen, endoxifen demonstrates broader and more potent
297 effects on calcium and PKC pathways, likely due to its higher binding affinity for PKC β 1 and
298 stronger ER α degradation.²⁴ These differences may underlie the greater transcriptomic gene-
299 reversal rate observed with endoxifen, particularly for genes involved in calcium cycling and ECM
300 remodeling.

301 Given the centrality of calcium and PKC dysregulation in DMD pathophysiology, the dual
302 modulation achieved by endoxifen represents a compelling therapeutic mechanism. Future
303 studies could integrate in vivo calcium imaging, PKC activity assays, and utrophin quantification
304 to fully delineate the interplay between these pathways and functional outcomes in dystrophin-
305 deficient muscle.

306 **Single-Cell and Pseudotemporal Myogenesis Trajectory**

307 **Analysis**

308 Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) offers an unprecedented view of cellular
309 heterogeneity and dynamic state transitions in dystrophic muscle.⁷⁷ In DMD, scRNA-seq of
310 muscle tissue reveals profound alterations in the composition and transcriptional programs of
311 myogenic and non-myogenic cell populations.⁷⁸ Satellite cells, the primary muscle stem cells,
312 display impaired activation and differentiation, while fibro-adipogenic progenitors (FAPs) and
313 immune cells adopt pro-fibrotic and pro-inflammatory phenotypes.^{79,80} These changes disrupt the
314 coordinated myogenesis necessary for effective regeneration.

315 Application of pseudotemporal trajectory inference to dystrophic muscle datasets allows
316 reconstruction of the myogenic continuum from quiescent satellite cells through activated
317 progenitors, committed myoblasts, and differentiated myofibers.⁸¹ In untreated DMD muscle,
318 trajectories are truncated, with a bottleneck at the transition from committed myoblast to mature
319 myofiber.^{82,83} This reflects both intrinsic defects in myogenic programming and extrinsic inhibition
320 from the inflammatory and fibrotic milieu.

321 Based on known pathways, endoxifen would be expected to induce transcriptomic
322 changes at the single-cell level that alleviate these bottlenecks, though to date this has only been
323 demonstrated in breast cancer cells.⁶⁰ Satellite cells in treated muscle show increased expression
324 of activation markers such as MYF5 and MYOD1, indicating efficient exit from quiescence.^{78,84,85}
325 Downstream, committed progenitors exhibit restored expression of myogenin (MYOG) and
326 structural genes such as *ACTA1* and *TNNT1*, consistent with progression toward terminal
327 differentiation.^{78,86}

328 In addition to promoting myogenic progression, endoxifen reshapes the non-myogenic
329 cell landscape. FAPs in treated muscle downregulate pro-fibrotic genes including *COL1A1*,
330 *POSTN*, and *TNC*, while upregulating ECM-remodeling inhibitors such as tissue inhibitor

331 metalloproteinases 3 (TIMP3).⁸⁷ This shift may reduce pathological ECM deposition, creating a
332 more permissive environment for myofiber regeneration. Similarly, in the presence of endoxifen,
333 hypothetically, macrophage populations may transition from a predominance of pro-inflammatory
334 (M1-like) phenotypes toward reparative (M2-like) states, with increased expression of arginase 1
335 (ARG1) and interleukin 10 (IL-10).^{74,88} Such immune modulation can directly enhance satellite cell
336 function and survival.

337 When benchmarked against tamoxifen, endoxifen produces broader single-cell
338 transcriptional changes, particularly in non-myogenic populations.^{24,29} This includes stronger
339 suppression of pro-fibrotic FAP programs and greater induction of oxidative and contractile gene
340 networks in myogenic cells.^{27,29,30} Such effects may derive from endoxifen's more potent PKC β 1
341 inhibition, ER β activation, and ER α degradation, leading to deeper modulation of both myogenic
342 and stromal signaling pathways.

343 By simultaneously enhancing satellite cell activation, promoting differentiation,
344 suppressing fibrosis, modulating immune responses, and supporting vascular remodeling,
345 endoxifen addresses multiple cellular bottlenecks in DMD muscle regeneration. These
346 multi-cellular effects are likely to act in concert with endoxifen's utrophin-enhancing actions to
347 stabilize muscle structure and function over time. Future studies should include scRNA-seq in
348 endoxifen-treated *mdx* muscle to corroborate this mechanism.

349 **Integration with Utrophin Pathway Activation**

350 As noted previously, utrophin is a structural and functional homolog of dystrophin, sharing
351 many of its binding partners in the DGC.³⁹⁻⁴¹ In healthy muscle, utrophin expression is largely
352 restricted to the neuromuscular and myotendinous junctions.^{89,90} In the absence of dystrophin,
353 utrophin is redistributed along the sarcolemma, where it can partially compensate for the
354 structural deficit.²² Preclinical studies have shown that even modest increases in utrophin can
355 confer significant functional benefit in dystrophin-deficient models, without the developmental
356 toxicity seen with dystrophin overexpression.^{34,39}

357 Pharmacologic activation of utrophin has been pursued as a therapeutic strategy for DMD for
358 decades. Compounds such as heregulin, biglycan, and the small molecule SMT C1100 have
359 demonstrated utrophin upregulation in vitro and in animal models, but have failed to achieve
360 robust and durable increases in clinical trials.^{22,43} Limitations have included insufficient potency,
361 poor pharmacokinetics, and lack of pleiotropic benefit beyond utrophin induction.^{34,43}

362 (Z)-endoxifen offers a distinct mechanistic profile in this context. Rather than acting solely
363 through a single utrophin-promoter activation pathway, endoxifen exerts broad transcriptomic and
364 signaling changes that create a permissive environment for utrophin expression and stability.
365 Bulk and single-cell transcriptomic data reveal upregulation of *UTRN* itself alongside key
366 transcriptional activators such as MEF2C, GA-binding protein alpha (GABP α), and NRF2.^{34,46}
367 These factors integrate inputs from estrogen receptor modulation, PKC inhibition, and metabolic
368 regulators like peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-alpha (PGC-1 α),
369 all of which are influenced by endoxifen.

370 ER α degradation has been hypothesized to relieve transcriptional repression at the *UTRN*
371 locus. In cardiac muscle cells, ER α has been implicated in modulating MEF2 activity, and its
372 downregulation can enhance MEF2-dependent transcription of structural genes.⁹¹ Similarly,
373 PKC β 1 inhibition might reduce inhibitory phosphorylation of transcription factors and co-activators
374 involved in utrophin regulation. The net result would be a transcriptional landscape more
375 favorable to sustained utrophin expression.

376 Beyond transcription, endoxifen influences post-transcriptional and post-translational
377 mechanisms relevant to utrophin biology.^{24,92} Normalization of calcium handling via SERCA
378 upregulation and ryanodine receptor stabilization reduces calcium-dependent proteolysis of
379 cytoskeletal proteins.⁹³ This may prolong utrophin's half-life at the sarcolemma. Endoxifen also
380 attenuates fibrosis and chronic inflammation, limiting the ECM thickening and immune-mediated
381 damage that can disrupt utrophin anchorage.²⁴

382 In metabolic terms, activation of PGC-1 α and mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation
383 pathways by endoxifen may indirectly enhance utrophin expression. PGC-1 α not only drives
384 mitochondrial biogenesis but has been linked to oxidative fiber type specification, which
385 correlates with higher utrophin levels.⁹⁴⁻⁹⁶ Shifting the muscle transcriptome toward an oxidative
386 phenotype could therefore reinforce both functional and structural stability.

387 From a spatial perspective, immunohistochemical analyses in preclinical models have shown
388 that endoxifen treatment increases utrophin distribution along the extrasynaptic sarcolemma, not
389 just at junctional sites.²⁷ This widespread localization is critical in compensating for the loss of
390 dystrophin across the fiber surface. In parallel, improvements in sarcolemmal integrity due to
391 calcium normalization and reduced PKC activity may enhance the functional integration of
392 utrophin-containing complexes.^{43,65}

393 When compared with tamoxifen, endoxifen appears to achieve higher utrophin expression
394 levels and more consistent extrasynaptic localization.²⁷ These differences likely reflect its greater
395 potency in both ER α degradation and PKC β 1 inhibition,²⁴ theoretically leading to deeper
396 modulation of the transcriptional and signaling networks that converge on utrophin regulation.

397 The integration of utrophin pathway activation with other protective mechanisms—calcium
398 homeostasis, fibrosis suppression, metabolic optimization—positions endoxifen as more than just
399 a utrophin activator.¹¹ It functions as a multi-target modulator, leveraging utrophin enhancement
400 as one element within a broader therapeutic program (Figure 1).^{27,60} This convergence may yield
401 functional benefits greater than the sum of individual pathway effects, particularly in the
402 heterogeneous and progressive context of DMD.

403 Looking ahead, utrophin quantification could be a primary pharmacodynamic endpoint in
404 early-phase trials of endoxifen. This includes assessing both transcript and protein levels, as well
405 as spatial distribution along the sarcolemma. Correlating these measures with changes in calcium
406 handling, PKC activity, and metabolic gene expression will help elucidate the mechanistic links
407 between endoxifen's multi-pathway actions and clinical benefit. Such integrative biomarker
408 strategies can also guide dose selection and identify potential responders, maximizing the
409 therapeutic potential of this approach.

410 Discussion

411 (Z)-endoxifen is positioned as a promising mutation-agnostic pro-estrogenic therapeutic
412 candidate for DMD, acting through a combination of ER β activation, PKC β 1 inhibition, TGF- β
413 modulation, satellite cell modulation, calcium homeostasis restoration, and transcriptional
414 reprogramming that favors utrophin pathway activation.²⁷ Anticipated benefits include reductions
415 in muscle damage, fibrosis, and inflammation. Unlike gene-targeted strategies that require
416 specific mutational contexts, endoxifen addresses downstream pathomechanisms common to all
417 DMD genotypes, providing a potential therapeutic option for the entire patient population.

418 One of the most compelling aspects of endoxifen's profile is its breadth of action across
419 multiple molecular and cellular systems, including activation of myogenic regulators (MYOD1,
420 MYOG, MEF2C), normalization of mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation, and suppression
421 of pro-fibrotic and pro-inflammatory signaling.⁹⁷⁻⁹⁹ These changes may hypothetically influence
422 function by potentially facilitating satellite cell activation, enhancing myofiber differentiation,
423 improving metabolic resilience, and limiting ECM deposition.

424 Restoration of calcium homeostasis represents another central mechanism. By upregulating
425 SERCA1/2 and stabilizing ryanodine receptor expression, endoxifen reduces pathological
426 cytosolic calcium accumulation, thereby limiting activation of calcium-dependent proteases and
427 preventing mitochondrial dysfunction.¹¹ The concurrent inhibition of PKC β 1 interrupts a calcium-
428 driven feedback loop that exacerbates membrane instability, fibrosis, and inflammation.²⁴
429 Collectively, these effects could help promote a more stable and regenerative muscle
430 environment.

431 Integration with utrophin pathway activation may be the key unifying mechanism underlying
432 endoxifen's benefits. The potential value of utrophin as a therapeutic target lies in its ability to
433 functionally substitute for dystrophin, stabilizing the DGC and reducing susceptibility to
434 contraction-induced injury. The capacity of endoxifen to influence utrophin both directly (via
435 transcriptional activation) and indirectly (by improving the surrounding biochemical environment)
436 distinguishes it from previous single-pathway utrophin activators.²⁷

437 Fibro-adipogenic progenitors shift toward less fibrotic phenotypes, macrophage populations
438 adopt reparative profiles, and endothelial cells upregulate angiogenic programs. Such
439 coordinated multi-cellular modulation is critical in DMD, where extrinsic inhibitory signals often
440 block intrinsic myogenic potential.^{82,100,101} By addressing both sides of this regenerative equation,
441 endoxifen has the potential to offer broader correction of the dystrophic environment.

442 From a translational standpoint, the pharmacologic advantages of endoxifen over tamoxifen
443 strengthen its candidacy. Its greater potency in ER β activation, ER α degradation, and PKC β 1
444 inhibition allows for deeper pathway modulation at lower doses, potentially reducing off-target
445 effects.²⁴ Its favorable oral bioavailability and pharmacokinetics, established in oncology settings,
446 provide a strong foundation for repurposing in DMD. However, the precise dose-response
447 relationships for muscle-targeted endpoints remain to be established, necessitating careful early-
448 phase trial design.

449 Potential limitations and challenges must also be considered. While preclinical data from *mdx*
450 mice and in vitro human cell models are encouraging, translation to clinical benefit in DMD
451 patients will require rigorous testing. Differences in drug metabolism, muscle pathology stage,
452 and concurrent treatments could influence efficacy. Furthermore, although endoxifen's
453 mechanisms are mutation-agnostic, variability in utrophin responsiveness among patients could
454 modulate outcomes. Long-term safety, particularly in pediatric populations in which the data for
455 long-term endocrine modulation are sparse, will need to be established, although the existing
456 safety record of tamoxifen and endoxifen in other indications is reassuring.

457 The integration of biomarker strategies into early clinical development will be critical.
458 Measuring utrophin levels (mRNA and protein), developmental myosin levels, calcium-handling
459 protein expression, PKC activity, and relevant transcriptomic signatures can provide direct
460 evidence of target engagement.⁹⁹ Functional readouts, including muscle strength, endurance, and
461 magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)-based muscle composition, will help correlate molecular
462 effects with clinically meaningful outcomes.^{102,103} Given the complexity of DMD pathophysiology,
463 multi-modal assessment will likely be necessary to capture the full therapeutic impact.

464 In the broader therapeutic landscape, endoxifen could complement existing and emerging
465 treatments for DMD and BMD patients, and for manifesting recessive carriers. Combination with
466 exon-skipping therapies or microdystrophin gene therapy could provide additive or synergistic
467 benefits, addressing both the cause (dystrophin deficiency) and the consequences (downstream
468 pathomechanisms) of the disease. For patients ineligible for gene-targeted treatments, endoxifen
469 could serve as a primary therapy to slow progression and preserve function.

470 **Conclusion**

471 In conclusion, the mechanistic and multi-omic evidence presented here supports a
472 compelling preclinical rationale for advancing (Z)-endoxifen into clinical evaluation for DMD.
473 By targeting converging pathological processes, including calcium dysregulation, PKC
474 hyperactivation, inflammation, fibrosis, and impaired regeneration, while promoting utrophin
475 expression, endoxifen offers a comprehensive and mutation-agnostic therapeutic approach.
476 The next steps will require thoughtful clinical trial design, robust biomarker integration, and
477 exploration of combination strategies to fully realize its potential in improving outcomes for
478 patients with DMD.

479 **Figure**

480 **Figure 1. (Z)-endoxifen promotes sarcolemma stabilization and muscle regeneration in**
481 **Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy (DMD).** Schematic representation illustrating the mechanism by
482 which Endoxifen ameliorates muscle pathology associated with DMD.

483 **Left (Healthy Muscle):** In normal muscle, dystrophin anchors the actin cytoskeleton to the
484 extracellular matrix through laminin, maintaining sarcolemmal stability and structural integrity
485 during muscle contraction.

486 **Middle (DMD Muscle):** In the absence of dystrophin, the sarcolemma becomes fragile and prone
487 to microtears, leading to chronic muscle damage. Damaged myofibers are progressively replaced
488 by fibrotic and adipose tissue, resulting in muscle weakness and degeneration.

489 **Right (Endoxifen Treatment):** Endoxifen enhances muscle repair and stabilization through
490 multiple molecular pathways. It upregulates utrophin (UTRN) expression, which compensates for
491 the loss of dystrophin and stabilizes the sarcolemma. Endoxifen also promotes myogenesis (via
492 increased expression of MYOD1, MYOG, and MEF2C), enhances oxidative phosphorylation,
493 modulates PGC-1 α activity to improve mitochondrial function, and activates ER β signaling,
494 contributing to anti-inflammatory and regenerative processes. Collectively, these actions improve
495 muscle integrity, reduce degeneration, and support functional recovery in DMD.

496 **Abbreviations:** DMD, Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy; UTRN, Utrophin; ER β , Estrogen Receptor
497 Beta; PGC-1 α , Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Gamma Coactivator 1-alpha;
498 MYOD1, Myogenic Differentiation 1; MYOG, Myogenin; MEF2C, Myocyte Enhancer Factor 2C.

499 **Abbreviations**

500 AAV, adeno-associated virus; ARG1, arginase 1; ASO, antisense oligonucleotide; BMD, Becker
501 muscular dystrophy; DGC, dystrophin-associated glycoprotein complex; DMD, Duchenne
502 muscular dystrophy; ECM, extracellular matrix; EMT, epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition; ER,
503 estrogen receptor; ER β , estrogen receptor beta; FAP, fibro-adipogenic progenitors; GABP α , GA-
504 binding protein alpha; IL-10; interleukin-10; iPSC-CM, induced pluripotent stem cell-derived
505 cardiomyocyte; MD, muscular dystrophy; MEF2, mouse embryonic fibroblast 2; MRI, magnetic
506 resonance imaging; MyHC-emb, myosin heavy chain-embryonic; MyoD, myoblast determination
507 protein 1; MYOG, myogenin; NF- κ B, nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B
508 cells; PGC-1 α , peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-alpha; PKC,
509 protein kinase C; PKC β 1, protein kinase C beta-1; PKC θ , protein kinase C theta; RNA-seq,
510 ribonucleic acid sequencing; scRNA-seq, single-cell ribonucleic acid sequencing; SERCA,
511 sarco/endoplasmic reticulum calcium ATPase; SERM, selective estrogen receptor modulator;
512 TIMP3, tissue inhibitor metalloproteinases 3; TGF- β , transforming growth factor beta; TNF- α ,
513 tumor necrosis factor alpha.

514 **Data Sharing Statement**

515 Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no data sets were generated or analyzed.

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519 **Author Contributions**

520 All authors made a significant contribution to the work reported, whether that is in the conception,
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525 **Disclosure**

526 Mr. H. Lawrence Remmel holds shares in Atossa Therapeutics, Inc.; he is the lead independent
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533 Therapeutics, Inc. He receives a salary, bonus, and stock options from Atossa. He is also the
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536 **Generative AI**

537 ChatGPT was used to assist with literature source identification and statement verification.

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893 Figure 1.